

LIGNIN FIBERS FOR GREEN NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Composite manufacturing technology has developed to take advantage of different materials to reach the desired functionality. Polymeric composites made from petroleum-based matrix and reinforcements have been widely studied and developed. However, the recent movement towards renewability and sustainability of resources has also been entered this industry.

Although utilizing renewable resource based materials for composite production seems interesting, it is challenging to find highly available and low cost resources which at the same time meet the required process-ability.

Cellulosic ethanol is a rapidly growing industry as a solution to some of the environmental issues. However, this industry produces a large amount of a coproduct which is currently just burned to produce energy or is disposed of as landfill, and it should be utilized in other applications to improve the economics of this process [1].

For the production of ethanol from cellulosic material, the structure of the biomass is initially broken in a pretreatment stage to separate the lignin from cellulose and hemicellulose. Then the produced mixture is hydrolyzed to convert the cellulose and hemicellulose to fermentable sugars which are dissolved in an aqueous medium and sent to the fermentation. The solid residue of the hydrolysis stage is the coproduct of this process. Analysis of this material shows the presence of lignin and residues of carbohydrates [2]. Lignin is a three dimensional aromatic polymer which has a carbon rich structure. During the pretreatment, the structure of lignin breaks, resulting in the reduction of the molecular weight of this material. Variability in the bioethanol feedstock and processing conditions cause a large variability in the properties of this material. Lignin has the potential to be used as a low cost raw material to produce fibers/carbon fibers to

replace the petroleum-based fibers used as composite reinforcements [3].

Among the several spinning technologies, melt spinning and electrospinning of lignin have been studied [4,5]. For the spinning of lignin, its blending with a synthetic polymer is required to achieve the spinnability. Compared to melt spinning, electrospinning has the advantage of being faster, and has the ability to control the diameter and produce nanoscale fibers. Furthermore, it can be done in room temperature so removing the challenges regarding high processing temperatures of synthetic polymers and degradability of lignin in those temperatures.

In this study, electrospinning of lignin blends with poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) has been investigated. Lignin source is a cellulosic ethanol byproduct. This byproduct is the solid residue of the enzymatic hydrolysis stage in the ethanol production. More specifically, lignin and carbohydrates were separated from each other in a steam explosion process followed by enzymatic hydrolysis of the cellulose. The solid residue of the hydrolysis stage which is separated from the liquid containing the fermentable sugars makes the byproduct of this process.

After solvent extraction of lignin from the byproduct, the solution was mixed with PEO and electrospun. Effect of different amounts of PEO and its molecular weight on the fiber formation are studied. Furthermore, the effect of changing the feeding rate and the voltage on the morphology of the fibers were studied.

2 Materials and Methods

Solid residue of enzymatic hydrolysis of Poplar was received from Mascoma, Canada. This material is named as hydrolysis lignin. Since it is an industrial product, it has multiple constituents such as lignin, un-hydrolyzed cellulose and carbohydrates, residues

of sugars, and also residues of enzymes and processing additives. To remove the sugars and water soluble impurities, the material was washed in water at $T = 60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (the ratio of material to water was 1g in 100mL) and then dried in oven at $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then lignin was extracted from the washed and dried material by refluxing in N,N-dimethyl formamide (DMF, from Sigma-Aldrich) for 24 hours. In the next step, the solution was filtered and therefore two fractions were obtained: a soluble fraction, and an insoluble solid residue. The solvent was dried to obtain the soluble fraction for further characterization. The soluble and insoluble fractions in DMF were further analyzed to confirm the lignin composition of the soluble fraction.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis was performed by a Thermo Scientific–Nicolet 6700 FTIR spectrometer in attenuated total reflection infrared (ATR-IR) mode to study the functional groups of the compounds. The lignin content of the byproduct material and its soluble and insoluble fractions was measured following the NREL method, “Determination of structural carbohydrates and lignin in biomass” (NREL/TP-510-42618, Revised 2010) [6-8].

Glass transition temperature of the samples was measured by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) (TA Instruments – DSC Q200). 5–6 mg of each sample was heated in closed aluminum pans, under a nitrogen atmosphere (flow rate: 50 mL min^{-1}). Samples were heated from $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/min}$, cooled to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a rate of $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/min}$, then again heated to $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C/min}$.

The molecular weight of the washed hydrolysis lignin, and its soluble and insoluble fractions in DMF, were measured by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) using three Styragel HR columns (Waters), HR 0.5, 1, 2 in series and tetrahydrofuran as the mobile phase with a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min . Samples were acetylated prior to the analysis. For acetylation, 0.5 g of each sample was dissolved in 6 mL pyridine/acetic anhydride (1:1 volume ratio) and stirred for one week. Then the acetylated material was precipitated by adding the solution drop wise into 100 mL ice-water containing 1 mL hydrochloric acid (HCl). Then the precipitated material was filtered and dried [9].

Solutions for electrospinning were a mixture of lignin and PEO in DMF. The effect of two different

molecular weights of PEO on the fiber formation was studied. The two PEO molecular weights were $200,000\text{ g/mol}$ and $5,000,000\text{ g/mol}$. Lignin to PEO ratios in the solutions were varied from 95/5 to 80/20 and total polymer concentration was kept at 4 wt%.

Electrospinning was performed in a NANON-01 electrospinning machine (MECC CO) with vertical set up. Flow rate and spinneret height were fixed at 0.3 mL/hr and 20 cm , respectively. Effect of voltage on fiber diameter was studied.

Morphology of the spun samples was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FEI Company – Inspect S50). Images were analyzed by ImageJ 1.45s software. Average of diameter of 50 points of the fibers is reported as the average fiber diameter.

3 Results and Discussion

The percentage of solubility of the hydrolysis lignin in DMF was 43 %. Results of the lignin content measurement of the hydrolysis lignin and its soluble and insoluble fractions, and also molecular weight of each fraction is reported in Table 1.

It was observed that lignin extraction by DMF, cannot separate all the lignin and some still remains in the insoluble fraction. These are probably very high molecular weight components or maybe they have some chemical bonding with the residual carbohydrates. Molecular weight of the different fractions was measured after acetylation of the material. This method, however, has limitations especially for hydrolysis lignin and its insoluble fraction which are complex mixtures of lignin with other compounds. Generally, it is expected that acetylated lignin becomes completely soluble in the mobile phase of GPC. However, the hydrolysis lignin and the insoluble fraction were not completely soluble after acetylation. Therefore, the measured molecular weight cannot show the real value but it can be used as an estimation of the M.W. of the material. Comparing the results in Table 1 shows that the hydrolysis lignin has the highest M_w , followed by the insoluble fraction and soluble fraction. It is consistent with the solubility results. The highest molecular weight fractions cannot dissolve in DMF and stay in the insoluble fraction. However, the soluble fraction has a higher M.W.

compared to the Kraft lignin such as Indulin AT, which is reported to have a M_w of 3,700 g/mol [5]. Further analysis of the soluble fraction and comparison with the insoluble material and hydrolysis lignin was performed by FTIR (Fig. 1). FTIR graphs have similar shapes with some differences. The soluble sample has a peak at 2930 with a smaller shoulder at 2850 cm^{-1} . These peaks are due to CH vibrations in aromatic methoxyl groups and methyl groups in the side chains of lignin. The insoluble sample and hydrolysis lignin have a single peak at 2900 cm^{-1} , which is similar to peaks of cellulose in this region [10]. The hydroxyl groups vibrations occur at 3400 cm^{-1} for lignins and at 3350 cm^{-1} for cellulose [11,12]. It is observed that the peaks in these regions for soluble fraction is showing the behavior of lignins while for the hydrolysis lignin and the insoluble fraction, the peaks of cellulose are overlapping the lignin peaks.

The region below 1400 cm^{-1} provides information about structural units of lignin [11]. The aromatic ring in syringyl and guaiacyl units results in absorption at 1324 cm^{-1} [11,13] for soluble samples while cellulose has a doublet at 1335 and 1316 cm^{-1} [14]. For the insoluble sample and hydrolysis lignin, peaks of cellulose overlap the lignin peak at 1324 cm^{-1} , and so the superposition of peaks appears as a sharper peak and a shoulder. Soluble sample and hydrolysis lignin exhibit characteristic peaks of guaiacyl units. These peaks appear at 1267, 1147, and 829 cm^{-1} due to ring and C=O stretching and CH vibrations [10,11]. The spectra of hydrolysis lignin and insoluble samples have weak peaks at 829 cm^{-1} and a band at 900 cm^{-1} which is because of C-O-C stretching in the cellulose spectrum [12,15].

After confirmation of the lignin structure of the soluble fraction, thermal properties of the fractions were studied. Fig. 2 shows the DSC of the samples. In the first heating cycle, there is a big peak due to water vaporization from the material [16, 17]. Glass transition temperature (T_g) can be measured from the second cycle. This property for the hydrolysis lignin and its soluble fraction are 164, and 154 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. The insoluble fraction does not show a significant glass transition under this heating history. The reason is the interaction between lignin and the carbohydrates which hinders the movements of the chains. The same reason explains the higher amount of T_g for the soluble fraction compared to the

hydrolysis lignin. The high values of the T_g for the soluble lignin is one of the advantages of this material for the fiber production. It can facilitate the further carbonization of the fibers.

For the electrospinning of lignin, different amounts of PEO were added to the solution and effect of solution composition and also processing parameters on the morphology of the fibers were studied.

Fig. 3 shows the formation of spherical particles from electrospinning of a solution of 4 % lignin without addition of PEO. Although different voltages and feed rates were applied, lignin by itself cannot create enough elasticity to form a continuous jet, which is required for the fiber formation.

In the next stage, PEO is added to the solution. Solution with 4 % (lignin/PEO:80/20) with two different molecular weight of PEO were spun (Fig. 4). PEO with lower molecular weight only produces small particles with diameters in the range of $0.641 \pm 0.172 \mu\text{m}$ while upon increasing the molecular weight to 5,000,000 g/mol continuous fibers with diameters in the range of $0.478 \pm 0.099 \mu\text{m}$ are formed. Total polymer concentration was further increased to 5%, and fiber morphology could be collected.

The lignin to PEO ratio was increased to 90/10 and 95/5 and higher molecular weight of PEO was tested. SEM images of the spun fibers are shown in Fig. 5. It is observed that upon increasing the lignin content, the morphology is changing from smooth fibers to beaded fibers and then particles. Increasing the lignin reduces the elasticity of the solution and therefore it cannot be stretched by the electrical forces.

The effects of changing the feed rate and voltage on the fiber morphology was studied by collecting the samples at three different voltages of 10, 13, and 16 kV and feed rates of 0.1, and 0.4 mL/hr. The results are shown in Fig. 6.

Comparison of the fiber diameters at each voltage shows that with increasing the flow rate the fiber diameters are decreased. It is usually expected that increase in the flow rate corresponds to more solution coming out of the needle which results in the increase in the diameter. However, sometimes the role of the charges carried by the solution is more significant. The explanation for the observed reduction in this experiment is the increased charge density on the flow with increasing the flow rate. At

a critical flow rate this increased charge density results in the reduction in the fiber diameter [18]. Increasing the flow rate also increases the amount of solvent which should be vaporized. At the same time, higher voltage accelerates the moving of the solution jet resulting in a shorter flight time. As a result of these two effects, it is observed that at higher feed rate and voltage ($F = 0.4$ mL/hr and $V = 13$ and 16 kV) the fibers start to fuse and melt together, especially at the points they fall on each other. At each flow rate, increasing the voltage reduces the fiber diameter which is due to the higher forces applied to the jet. However, it also occurs at the same time as reducing the flight time and less time for drying the fibers. As a result, if the spinning is performed in a humid condition which hampers the solvent evaporation, it may result in the fusion and melting the fibers. Depending on the solvent vapor pressure and the humidity, flow rate and voltage this phenomena can be severe to an extent which no fiber forms [19].

Conclusions

In this work, lignin was extracted from an industrial byproduct by a solvent extraction method. The solution was directly used for electrospinning. From about 60% of lignin available in the byproduct, about 40% is soluble. Although it is a small amount and preparing the solutions with high concentrations become difficult, electrospun fiber could be produced by addition of PEO with a high molecular weight. The main disadvantage of directly using the bioethanol byproduct as a source of lignin is its low solubility. Therefore, making solutions with high lignin concentration requires a large amount of solvent. For each concentration which could produce fibers, effect of different voltage levels on fiber diameter was analyzed. It was observed that a combination of blend ratio, polymer concentration, and processing voltage and feeding rate together determine the diameter. Molecular weight of lignin indirectly affects the process by changing the rheological properties.

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Table 1 – Lignin content and molecular weight of hydrolysis lignin and its soluble and insoluble fractions in DMF.

	Lignin content (%)	M _n (Daltons)	M _w (Daltons)	M _w /M _n
Hydrolysis lignin	62.5 ± 0.6	4,535	8,521	1.8
Soluble fraction	92.9 ± 0.4	3,421	5,308	1.5
Insoluble fraction	43 ± 1.9	3,969	7,448	1.8

Fig. 1. FTIR analysis of the hydrolysis lignin (H.L.), its soluble (Sol. H.L.) and insoluble (Insol. H.L.) fractions in DMF.

Fig. 2. Differential scanning calorimetry of the hydrolysis lignin and its soluble and insoluble fractions. The graphs only show the second heating cycle.

Fig. 3. SEM images of spherical particles of electrospun lignin.

Fig. 4. SEM images of electrospinning of solutions of 4% (lignin/PEO : 80/20) with two different molecular weight of PEO (a) M.W. (PEO) = 200,000 and (b) M.W. (PEO) = 5,000,000. Feed rate = 0.7 mL/hr and voltage = 18 kV.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the electrospun fibers from solution of 5% (lignin/PEO), molecular weight of PEO = 5,000,000 with ratios of (a) 80/20, (b) 90/10, (c) 95/5. Feed rate = 0.7 mL/hr and voltage = 13 kV.

Fig. 6. Effect of varying voltage and feed rate on the fiber morphology. Spinning solution was a 5% (lignin/PEO:80/20) and PEO molecular weight was 5,000,000. Tip to collector distance = 23 cm and temperature = 24 °C and humidity = 44%.